

ERC Starting Grant 2025
Part B2
(not evaluated in Step 1)

Section a. State-of-the-art and objectives

a.1. Background and objectives. Speaking about any human being – a real or an imaginary one, someone one knows or someone who died hundreds of years ago – one has a rather large choice of linguistic labels (ex. Erasmus of Rotterdam according to English Wikipedia page¹, Figure 1). Among these labels, there are personal names, pronouns and **human nouns** (henceforth, **HN**) – common nouns that refer to human beings in all types of contexts.

Though numerous studies in pragmatics and linguistic anthropology have considered HN as terms of address or looked into kinship terminology (see a.2. Project in respect to the state of the art), HN as a lexicon and its usage have been so far largely overlooked. It is easy to notice, however, that, even when speaking about a human being that is out of sight, someone from the past, or an imaginary character, one has a rather large panel of linguistic labels.

The choice of the precise label in the given utterance is never random, and, above the descriptive function, is conditioned by both the speaker's and his addressee's identities, their relationship and the pragmatic aim of the utterance. As Dahlgren (1985: 381) puts it, "persons are conceived in a richer and more complex way than the physical objects". Indeed, while speaking about the outer world is less emotionally challenging, labelling another human being is a result of a more complex operation that includes expressing your relation to the human being while addressing another human being.

I argue, therefore, that a thorough study of HN as a lexicon can offer a powerful and yet underexploited way of understanding social relations, hierarchies and their evolution. HumaNS-CHANGE's aim will be to prove this claim on the example of the HN lexicon in Medieval French (9th-15th century).

I have been working on the historical semantics and pragmatics of different HN in Medieval French since the second year of my Master's degree (Geylikman 2017a) studying:

- **'feudal' HN**: *baron, chevalier* (Geylikman 2017b, 2019, 2022b), *bachelier* (Geylikman 2018), *prince, duc, conte* (Geylikman 2020)
- **general HN**, e.g. general nouns (Schmid 2000) that refer to human beings without specifying any additional biological or social feature (Schnecker 2018a): *personne, homme, gens* (Geylikman 2024, in press, submitted)
- **terms of address** expressed by HN (Geylikman 2022a, in preparation).

Throughout my research, I have consistently considered the studied occurrences both in linguistic micro-context and narrative and socio-historical macro-context (Geylikman 2022b: 28-34). Although my perspective and methods were that of a linguist, I noticed that a thorough study of the HN usage reflected numerous social relations and hierarchies, as well as their evolution. This allowed me to make the following assumptions:

1. The HN lexicon changes and complexifies **along with social institutions**. During this process, certain subgroups of HN gain **performative force** (Austin 1962 and pragmatic tradition that followed), as they contribute to creating social realities.

Example: If at the starting *chevalier*, coming from Late Latin **caballarius*, meant "horseman" or "warrior who owns a horse", with the appearance of chivalry as institution, it gained a supplementary semantic feature characterizing the referent as a member of this institution (Geylikman 2022b). Therefore, as a part of the social practice of dubbing, *chevalier* gained performativity: one could only become *chevalier* if he was named so.

Figure 1

¹¹ Only a part of HN used in the Wikipedia article is included in Figure 1. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Erasmus>; illustration in figure 1 By School of Hans Holbein the Younger - The Yorck Project (2002) 10.000 Meisterwerke der Malerei (DVD-ROM), distributed by DIRECTMEDIA Publishing GmbH. ISBN: 3936122202., Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=152964>

2. The frequency and linguistic behaviour of HN depends on the **agency of power** of the referents, understood as the degree of power in a given social structure along with the capacity to exercise it (Ortner 2001; Ahearn 2001, see 112, 130-131).

Example: 12th century epic texts use the singular form of *baron* (eng. “high lord”) in 231 on a total of 287 occurrences (80%), whereas 12th century romance counts 262 on a total of 1105 occurrences (24%) which is a statistically significant difference (based on BFM22 material; calculated for singular vs plural forms: $\chi^2(1, N = 1392) = 321.0907, p \ll 0.00001$). It can be explained by the role assigned to the referents of *baron* in epic texts and romance respectively: while epic texts are written for and about *barons* – high lords – making them main characters in narration, in romance they become an anonymous audience witnessing the described events (Boutet & Strubel 1979; analysis in Geylikman 2022b).

3. The HN lexicon reflects **cultural representations** of the speakers understood as a set of norms and beliefs that are communicated repeatedly and, therefore, are distributed throughout a given social group (definition adapted from Sperber 1994: 162-163).

Example: Until law texts start to be written in French (and not only in Latin) in the 13th century, the ambiguous lexeme *homme* (“man as human being/man as male human being”) is enough to the lexical system, as the woman is considered as a marked case of a human being (Koch 2005: 18). Legal production requiring more objectivity, Old French loans for *personne* the use of *persona* from Latin legal texts in the meaning “any human being” for expressing social identity (Geylikman 2024)². Sometimes, the representations can be specific of a given genre: thus, singular subject case form of *baron*³ – *ber* – acquires positive connotation and then changes category towards a positive evaluative adjective in epic texts – the genre that is composed for and about the high lords, or *barons*. Nevertheless, this use does not spread in other genres targeting other social groups (Geylikman 2017a, 2019, 2022b).

This list could be continued by other assumptions. The choice of the word “assumption” is however deliberate: while the results of my research were interesting for the specific lexical items and their semantic change, such limited case studies did not allow generalizations about the whole HN lexicon. Moreover, whereas I found echoes to different aspects of my observations in a number of works (see a.2. Project in respect to the state of the art), they were case studies of specific lexemes, semantic fields or linguistic phenomena: comprehensive diachronic studies of HN lexica as a whole do not yet exist. It is not surprising, therefore, that my goal as a researcher is now to look at the big picture by investigating the HN lexicon as a representation of the society by itself.

When speaking about “representation”, especially in historical perspective, one needs though to be careful. Indeed, though the High Middle ages (1000-1300) which are partly covered by Medieval French, witnessed a considerable broadening of literacy beyond the Church, with better education for nobility (men and women) and opening of urban schools and universities, the majority of the population remained illiterate until the end of the studied period (see synthesis in *Britannica*’s entry on “education”⁴). Therefore, speaking of cultural representations, we must keep in mind that the written texts we have access to reflect the representations of the literate minority on themselves and the illiterate majority.

Nevertheless, I argue that, provided that their complexity is considered, texts in Medieval French offer valuable material for studying social change through linguistic labels attributed to humans. HumaNS-CHANGE goal will be to focus on linguistic usage and pragmatic aim of the utterances containing HN in order to test my main hypothesis: HN as a lexicon responds to social changes – embodying **agency of power** and social narratives – and drives them, serving as **performative** force that shapes **cultural representations**.

a.2. Project in respect to the state of the art

In this subsection I will sketch the state of the art in medieval studies, HN and, more generally, human reference studies in order to demonstrate that HumaNS-CHANGE builds up on a solid ground in social and human sciences while being innovative both in its object and goal.

² Sometimes we are lucky to find a confirmation to our modern analysis in metalinguistic reflexions of medieval scholars. Thus, Nicole Oresme, a counsellor to Charles V who lived in 14th century writes:

car *homo* signifie homme et femme et nul mot de françois ne signifie equipellenment. Et *animal* signifie toute chose qui a ame sensitive et sent quant l'en la touche. Et il n'est nul mot en françois qui ce signifie precisement. Et pour ce, ceste proposition est vraye : *mulier est homo*, et ceste est fausse : femme est homme. (BFM22, *Le Livre de Ethiques d'Aristote*, p.100) Eng. Because *homo* means man and woman and no French word has the same meaning. Et *animal* means everything that has a sensitive soul and feels when is touched. And there is not word in French that means it precisely. Et therefore, this proposition is true: *mulier est homo*, and this one is false: woman is man.

³ Old French having a partly viable case system (see Gröbl 2015 for an overview), *baron*’s paradigm is: Singular Subject: *ber*, Singular Object: *baron*, Plural Subject and Object: *barons*.

⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/education>. Accessed 8 October 2024, see reference in Resources.

Medieval French as a valid material for HN studies.

A state of language for which real-life utterances of communication are inaccessible may appear as an unusual choice for the study of performativity and social relations. Nevertheless, Medieval French appears particularly relevant for the study of HN in respect to social change for several reasons:

1. It includes three first stages of French language diachrony: Early Old French (9th – 11th century), Old French (12th – 13th century), Middle French (14th – 15th century) (see GGHF, 2020) which allows to put HN evolution in perspective of major linguistic changes, already extensively described by historical linguistics.

Among all the European medieval vernaculars, Old French is the largest judging by its text and manuscript traditions. Medieval French texts and their language have been extensively studied by philologists, linguists and palaeographers since 19th century; as a result, the linguistic evolution on all levels is synthetized in a number of manuals (Buridant 2019; GGHF 2020; Glessgen 2024) and its lexicon is described by dictionaries (FEW, DEAF, TL, AND, GdF, DMF). There is also a strong tradition of scientific edition of medieval manuscripts and printed books, and over past decades several electronic corpora have been built.

2. The history of the geographical zone covered by Medieval French is well documented and studied, which allows to confront the use of HN with what has been established about the evolution of social relations and hierarchies by historical science.

During the High Middle Ages and the Late Middle Ages (1100-1500), Medieval French roughly covered the northern part of the Kingdom of France, as well as the British Islands due to William the Conqueror's invasions; during 12th-13th century Crusades, it was also used as *lingua franca* in Crusader states in Eastern Mediterranean (see Glessgen 2024: 431-434).

Medieval studies of the Western Europe geographical zone have a long and rich tradition. Various aspects of social life and its evolution are studied by historians, archaeologists, philologists, paleographers, specialists in the history of art and literature. For instance, it is insightful to consult the program of the last edition of the International Medieval Congress (IMC Leeds)⁵ where identity studies are neighbouring those on the medieval image of the whale⁶. While all the aspects of the social life are important for the understanding of an ancient period in history, HumaNS-CHANGE will rely most on works that treat the questions of power, social institutions and cultural representations of the speakers (or, more precisely, writers) of Medieval French.

The question of **power** has been key to understanding social phenomena since the founding works in social sciences by Durkheim (1909) and Weber (1921). The concept of **agency**, which was introduced during 20th century (for theoretical basis, classifications and overview, see Ortner 2001, 2006a, 2006b; Ahearn 2001; Kockelman 2007), allowed to include language in the reflexion on structures of power and the way they are implemented. Thus, classic works in anthropology focus on the way dominated social groups compensate the lack of power through discourse and social practices (Scott 1985, 1990), as well as on linguistic coding of social positions and structures of power (Duranti 1994). As most of cross-disciplinary concepts, agency has multiple definitions; we follow Ahearn (2001) who, suggesting a rather broad understanding – “socio-culturally mediated capacity to act” (*op.cit.*: 112) – stresses the importance of specifying the type of agency that is studied for every given research (*op.cit.*: 130-131). HumaNS-CHANGE will be interested in the **agency of power** (Ortner 2001) – the degree of power in a given social structure along with the capacity to exercise it.

While certain recent works on Medieval History adopt agency perspective (Bouchard 2022, echoing Scott on medieval material), numerous studies explore power structures in general in medieval societies (for ex., Bisson 1995; Reynolds [1994] 2001) and describe **social institutions** – nobility, Church, serfdom – as well as their interrelations (Barthélemy 1990, 1997, 2003, 2007; Aurell 2011; Morsel 2004; Crouch 2005; Bouchard 1998, 2009, 2020).

3. The long diachrony of Medieval French witnesses the development of the written French standard through that of different genres – both fiction and non-fiction. Thus, various genres reflect **cultural representations** of the broadening literate minority.

Indeed, far from being a fair transcription of local linguistic varieties, it is considered as a developing linguistic standard which, but for the existence of several *scriptae* – regional writing traditions – remains relatively unified. At the same time, while at the beginning reading and writing was the prerogative of the Church, by the end of the medieval period a part of nobility started to read extensively and compose, while urban copying and, later, publishing hubs were thriving (Rey *et al.* 2007; GGHF 2020; Casal & Parussa 2022). Literary studies count abundant works dedicated to the “image” of different members of the Medieval society – the Knight (e.g. Köhler 1984; Chênerie [1986] 2014; Gingras 2011), the Dame (Rider &

⁵ Though IMC does not limit to Western Europe zone, the talks relative to this geographical zone seem more numerous.

⁶ See <https://urls.fr/3qqOup>

Friedman 2011; Benoît 2010), the Peasant (e.g. Zink 1986; Dufournet 1990; Lorcin 2011) *etc.* – and their relations in medieval literature. Furthermore, big names such as Marc Bloch [1939, 1940] 1994), Aron Gurevitch (1972), Jacques le Goff (2005, 2008, 2012), Georges Duby (1973), Jean-Claude Schmitt (1989, 2001, 2023), as well as works that followed (Gabriele & Stuckey 2008; Flori 2010), explore representations of different medieval social groups, as they can be deductible from texts – both fiction and documentary.

In conclusion, Medieval French and the geographical zone it covers is well-enough documented and described by all the disciplines HumaNS-CHANGE will address: linguistics, history, historical anthropology. The present state of those disciplines provides sufficient tools for large-scale lexical studies of Medieval French that take into account both linguistic micro-context and sociohistorical macro-context.

HN and reference to humans as a phenomenon

(1) *Case studies on HN.* When not considered as an independent lexicon, various HN have been studied across languages in numerous perspectives: as subgroups of common nouns, as terms of address, in respect to their morphology *etc.* It would be impossible to cite even a small part of them; instead we are going to list the angles under which HN have so far been considered and illustrate them by examples from French language studies which will be particularly useful for our project.

Morphology:

- derivation (Sleeman 2013; Flaux, Lagae & Stosic 2014; Huyghe & Tribout 2015, Schnedecker & Aleksandrova 2016; Amiot & Tribout 2018)
- grammaticalization (Giacalone-Ramat & Sanso 2007a, 2007b; Mihatsch 2017; Cappeau & Schnedecker 2015; Cappeau 2018).

Semantics, pragmatics and discourse analysis:

- semantic subclasses: e.g. role-nouns (Blanco I Escoda & Mejri 2006; Baider & Todirascu 2018); nouns of age, or ‘phase-nouns’ (Aleksandrova 2012, 2015, 2016) *etc.*
- gender and identity studies (Hellinger & Bussman 2002; Baider 2004; Fujimura 2005; Irmen & Kurovskaya 2010; Baider, Elmiger & Abbou 2012; Husson 2017; Viennot 2021)
- collective nouns (Flaux 1999; Lecolle 2023)
- evaluation expressed by nouns (Flaux & Mostrov 2016; Gosselin 2018; Lagorgette 2024).

An overview of bibliography on the recent state of the art in linguistic HN studies is provided by Schnedecker (2018b: 3-4 and bibliography thereof: 34-43).

In Medieval French studies numerous works on ‘feudal’ HN (e.g. *baron, chevalier, seigneur, vassal, sergent*) have appeared throughout 20th century (Hollyman 1957; Eskenazi 1976; Denis 1989; Scoones 1976). Among those we will stress studies on *chevalier* and *bachelier* (eng. “young knight”) in epic texts and romance by Jean Flori, rather unusual from a methodological point of view, as they attempt a historical investigation through fiction instead of documentary texts (Flori 1975a, 1975b). In an overall structuralist framework, certain lexemes have also been analysed as part of “semantic” or “lexical fields” and “vocabularies” (Venckeleer 1975; Picoche 1976; Matoré 1985). Nevertheless, with the exception of PI’s publications (Geylikman, 2020, 2022a, 2022b, 2024), no lexicological or semantic study of Medieval French period presents itself as a study of HN.

(2) *Reference to humans as a phenomenon*

In the introduction to the volume: ‘Person Reference: Linguistic, Cultural and Social Perspectives’, Stivers, Enfield & Levinson write:

Person reference is a subject that stands at a central intersection between the various behavioural sciences. How persons are classified and individuated lies at the heart of social theory; how different cultures do so has preoccupied anthropology; how we recognize them from face and voice is much investigated in psychology and the cognitive neurosciences; how we refer to persons has been a central topic in philosophy; and the grammatical machinery involved in tracking protagonists in discourse is an important topic in linguistics. Yet, despite the fact that person reference has this centrality, the empirical study of person reference in natural conversation – the central genre of language use – has been curiously neglected, particularly from a cross-cultural perspective that might throw much light on the relation between culture, social structure and language use (Stivers *et al.* 2007: 1)

Indeed, given that the object of social and human sciences is the human being itself, it is astonishing that linguistics expressions that denotes them have been so rarely studied as a whole. The ‘Person reference’ volume is one that comes the closest to HumaNS-CHANGE concerns in the linguistic anthropology field, as it examines the system of the reference to person – pronouns, kin terms, common nouns – in real-life interactions through several field case studies, mostly of small linguistic communities. Regardless of the high quality of the studies, as well as the relevance of suggested conclusions, this path has not been much followed so far. Another work that appears relevant in HumaNS-CHANGE perspective, is a study of the 3^d person reference in French parliamentary discourse by Truan (2021). Although the object of the study is

not a list of lexemes, but the overall linguistic expression of the 3^d person reference from discourse analysis perspective, it demonstrates clearly the pragmatic force of the reference to human beings outside direct address.

In the field of linguistics, apart several non-systematic works (Braun 1997, Gross 2008), it is to the **NHUMA project**⁷ that we can attribute the merit of proposing **HN lexicon** as a valid research object. Beyond numerous case studies by project members coming from different disciplines of linguistics, it produced several programmatic publications such as Schnedecker & Mihatsch (2018), Schnedecker (2018b) that demonstrate a finer semantic differentiation of HN in comparison to other lexica and propose a theoretical frame for HN studies. Moreover, Aleksandrova & Meyer (2021) highlight the relevance of HN as an object at cross-roads of social and human sciences: linguistics, anthropology, sociology, palaeontology. Nevertheless, the project did not last long enough to overcome some taxonomic issues. For instance, Huyghe, one of the NHUMA collaborators, nevertheless criticizes that type of ontological lexical classifications ('HN, artefact nouns' *etc.*) (2015: 8) placing most of HN among 'relational nouns' that combine agentivity and animate features (*op.cit.*: 16) and general HN among other general nouns (*op.cit.*: 20). All in all, the NHUMA project indubitably demonstrated the interest of HN for social and human sciences, but has not yet been conclusive at for the internal unity of the lexicon.

Above linguistic studies of HN, bibliography research traditions on three study objects will be essential for HumaNS-CHANGE methodology.

The first one is a subgroup of the HN lexicon: the **kinship terms** (*mother, father, daughter, brother etc.*). Those have been a key research object for anthropology from 19th century (Morgan 1871) and throughout 20th century with British school (Malinowski 1930; Evans-Pritchard 1951; Fortes 1969 *etc.*) and French school (Lévi-Strauss 1949 *etc.*) that both established the importance of kinship as a universal social institution. It remains an important object for social and human sciences until present day (see Déchaux 2008 on new kinship studies); no wonder *kinship studies* is one of the key-words for the ERC Starting Grant SH8 panel. From the second half of the 20th century, kinship as a study object spread throughout social and human resulting in works that suggest lexical classifications (Lounsbury 1966), define the role of language in the developing of kinship as social object (Danziger 2001), debate on its linguistic universality (Wierzbicka 2010, 2016; Passmore & Jordan 2020), and all in all demonstrate its importance in the social organization of any culture (Deliège 1996; Malone 2004; *etc.*). Kinship being studied across languages, cultures and historical periods, medieval studies have also made their contribution (Maranda 1974: ch. 1; O'Gorman 1988; Lett 2000, 2008; Le Jan 2003: ch. 5; Morsel 2017; Bouchard 2001, 2014).

Personal names, or nouns (names, surnames, nicknames *etc.*) as a study object have followed a similar path with extensive studies in linguistic anthropology (see a truly impressive bibliography on the subject in Chave-Dartoen, Leguy & Monnerie, 2012; Fine & Ouellette, 2005), history (for the Medieval period, Bourin 1990; Bourin & Chareille 1992; Patzold & Ubl 2014 that unites both lexica – kinship terms and personal names) and linguistics (to speak only of the French segment, Jonasson 1994; Van de Velde & Flaux 2000; Obry 2013 for Medieval romance). In the latter field, the works on personal names allowed to link logic/philosophy studies to semantics through reflexion on reference and denomination (see particularly Kleiber 1991, 1996). Beyond methodological benefits for studying the impact of linguistic usage on social organization and *vice-versa*, personal names studies appear particularly interesting as, according to Caro Reina (2022), in Romance languages, a subgroup of HN – human unique nouns (e.g. *king*) – have a morpho-syntactic behaviour similar to that of personal names.

The 'performative turn' in social and human sciences occurred along with the development of the Speech Act Theory (Austin, 1962; Searle, 1969), and the Politeness theory by Brown & Gilman (1960), then Brown & Levinson (1978, 1987). Those introduced social relations and structures of power in the study of speech (*cf.* pronouns of power vs pronouns of solidarity), as well as the distinction between *face threatening* and *face flattering acts*. The Politeness theory, in turn, originated a long line of studies of **terms of address** expressed by pronouns, personal names or common nouns, with linguistics, anthropology and identity studies being particularly sensitive to the topic (see Culpeper 2011). In French linguistics, Kerbrat-Orecchioni (1995, 2010) widely theorized the usage of terms of address for contemporary state of the language; one of the aspects that will be particularly useful for HumaNS-CHANGE is the concept of 'indirect address' – the act of speaking about a human being in third person, while being mindful of him listening/reading the message (Kerbrat-Orecchioni 2010). Regardless of the inaccessibility of actual speech, terms of address became also an object for historical linguistics, first with founder works on the English diachrony material (Jacobs & Jucker 1995; Jucker & Taavitsainen 2008; Jucker *et al.* 2010). As for Medieval French, though small case studies appeared sporadically throughout the second half of the 20th century

⁷ NHUMA = Les noms d'humains : de la description linguistique aux applications lexicographiques, <https://nomsdhumains.weebly.com/>

(e.g. Foulet 1950, Brereton 1958), the merit of a systematic description is to be attributed to Lagorrette (1994, 1998, 2006) who proposed a lexical classification and stressed the importance of the pragmatic value of the terms of address by adapting the framework of anglo-saxon pragmatics (Brown & Gilman, *op.cit.*, Brown & Levison, *op.cit.* etc) to Middle French material. Subsequently, Lagorrette conducted several studies focused particularly on insults in Medieval French (2003, 2013, 2016). Terms of address in Old French texts have also been explored, particularly, with respect to genre variation (Lehmann 2010; Denoyelle 2016; Geylikman 2022a).

Regardless of the relevance of those research traditions for studying the reference to humans, neither of them considers HN as a whole. All in all, in the current state of the art, HN as a lexicon appears to be

- underexploited by linguistics – because of the difficulty to find a strictly linguistic unity of the lexicon;
- overlooked by history – as it often focuses on specific social groups and phenomena;
- overlooked by anthropology – possibly, because of anthropology’s initial focus on small linguistic communities with less complex⁸ social organization, or phenomena like power or gender and oppositions they operationalize.

a.3 Proposal. I argue that the NHUMA project struggled to justify the homogeneity of the HN lexicon because its unity lays outside the proper linguistic level – as a cultural object that responds to and drives social evolution, alongside pronouns and personal names. The goal of HumaNS-CHANGE is to perform a multi-layered cross-disciplinary analysis of HN unravelling: stage A. *linguistic usage analysis*; stage B. *reviewing historical records*; stage C. *synthesis: linguistics, pragmatics, history, anthropology*.

Stage A. Linguistic usage analysis: thorough description of the linguistic usage of HN in respect to multiple linguistic features and extra-linguistic factors.

As the research question raises the issue of interdependence between language and society, it appears essential to start by a close examination of the usage: it will not be sufficient to consider only first attestations and meanings of the studied lexemes. In a more “anthropology style” perspective, in order to understand the people, we have to speak their language and listen to them: the only way we can do it for ancient societies is through description of linguistic usage that considers the specificity of the written texts it appears in.

Stage A. will be carried out:

- on a selected Medieval French corpus that will be representative of the development of the written standard and genres within.

A thorough knowledge of the texts by the collaborators will be essential for the success of Stage A. In addition to the metadata provided by electronic corpora, the open-access resource Arlima (<https://www.arlima.net/>) lists every Medieval French text that has so far been edited and provides extensive bibliography on the given text or author from various fields of medieval studies.

- considering every occurrence of a HN in a text as an utterance of communication including several participants and characterized by various parameters.

Figure 2 is a yet another distant child of the Jakobson model (1960) that we adapt to our immediate needs of studying HN as a cultural object. Every occurrence of a HN denotes a **referent**. While the level at which the reference is placed – linguistic or extralinguistic – has been an ongoing debate for decades (for an overview, see Kleiber 1997), in the present case, we use the term *referent* as the extra-linguistic entity – real or fictional – the speaker aims to point to by using the lexeme. Furthermore, every HN occurrence exists within **linguistic context**. The linguistic expression is used to describe an event – a real one or an imaginary one – in a given **setting** (or narrative context). In turn, the setting occurs in the frame of the **text** which –

⁸ 'Complex' is used in a non-evaluative sense, as having less levels and elements than, in this case, Medieval society.

both as a material and an immaterial object – is produced by the **speaker** and destined to the **addressee**. In this process, the speaker labels another human being (referent) while focusing on his communicative goal in respect to the addressee; both the speaker and the addressee have encyclopedic knowledge about the referent which influences their perception of the referent as another social actor.

In the present case, by “speaker” we mean of course “author”, which is a rather complex phenomenon when it comes to Medieval French, as it may include such instances as the actual author or translator – who are nevertheless often unknown – as well as the copyist(s), the editor(s), all of whom can manipulate the text at their convenience. In certain cases, the identity of the “addressee” – public, auditor or reader – is even more important than that of the “author”. For instance, while epic texts were destined to the high nobility, romance is known to have been composed for noblemen of a more modest situation – non-aristocrats or non-first born sons who could only count on themselves to rise in the social hierarchy through loyalty to a big lord or an advantageous marriage (Boutet & Strubel 1979); this difference partly explains that between narrative structure and motives of epic texts and romance. Many chronicles, scientific and didactical texts had sponsors among dukes, duchesses, which also oriented the writing in a certain way. Indeed, noble writers of memoirs and journals often take the side of their lords or kings while narrating (for example, Jean Froissart, relating the events of the Hundred Years’ War, takes the side of the counts of Hainaut, his protectors, see Courroux 2016: 339-351). At the same time, Church and nobility did not have the monopoly on text production: thus, *fabliaux* – 13th century short comic stories characterized by a crude humour - are known to be addressed to the urban audience and to express its world view. Therefore, even when analyzing narration segments in texts, we have to consider its addressee – those for whom the text is written.

Therefore, the aim of Stage A will be to describe the occurrence of a given lexeme in the frame of the corresponding situation of communication through features combining elements of distributional, sociolinguistic and pragmatic analysis (see table below). In order to do so, we will adapt to our needs the principle of usage-feature annotation for cognitive semantics used mostly for study of concepts and metaphors on the base of works by Geeraerts *et al*, 1994 and Gries 1999 that follow and perfect the Idealized Cognitive Model by Lakoff (1987). The relevance and predictability power of the usage-feature annotation has been recently demonstrated (Glynn 2009, 2010; Krawszak & Kokorniak 2012; Klavan 2014); moreover, the annotated datasets are easily adaptable to different kinds of categorical statistical analysis.

category	variables		annotation mode
corpus metadata	TEXT AUTHOR PUBLIC	genre, date of composition/manuscript, <i>scripta</i> ; author, scribe, social group author, gender author; social group addressee, author’s sponsor if applicable	automatic
linguistic usage	MORPHO SYNTAX SEMANTICS	case (for Old French), number, gender, affix syntactic function, 1 st /2 ^d /3 ^d person reference, determiners, modifiers (type + nature); class ¹⁰ , meaning, type of reference (general/specific)	automatic/ semi-automatic/ manual
referent and pragmatic value	REFERENT AGENCY SETTING PRAGMATICS	social group, gender, marital status role in narration; named/anonymous military campaign/courtship/trickery <i>etc.</i> ; evaluative(positive/negative)/neutral	semi-automatic/ manual

Figures 3-6 display an example of annotation of the following occurrence of *empereur* (eng. “emperor”) in the *Chanson de Roland*:

Li **empereres** Carles de France dulce
En cest pais nos est venuz cunfundre.
*Eng. The emperor Charles from sweet France
Came to defeat us in this country.*
Chanson de Roland, v.16-17, ed. G. Moignet

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J			
1	title	domain	genre	date_comp	date_ms	scripta	author	author_soc	author_gen	address_soc			
2	<i>Chanson de Roland</i>	fiction	epic	1100	1125	ang_nor	anon	none	none	arist			
	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W
1	case	number	affix	gender	syntax	person_ref	det_nature	det_type	mod_nature	mod_type	sem_class	meaning	reference
2	CSS	sing	none	masc	subject	3pers	art_def	le	none	none	role	empereur1	specific
	X	Y	Z	AA	AB	AC	AD						
	rt_soc	rt_gender	marital	role	pers_name	setting	prag						
	ROYAL	MASC	none	main	yes	council	neutral						

Figure 3-6

⁹ The use as TA (2^d person) would imply additional features describing the speaker, the addressee and their relationship.

¹⁰ Adapted from the NHUMA project classification of HN.

The completed annotation will allow to generate multiple frequency tables per century: for every item per features; for every genre – per lexeme; for every referent social group – per lexeme. At this step, through statistical analysis, we will detect the first significant oppositions that depend on one feature only: e.g., HN preferably used as terms of address *vs* HN preferably used as designation.

The next step will be to explore the dataset in order to find associations between the multiple variables described by annotation through multiple correspondence analyses, that will allow to detect big patterns (Glynn 2014). Subsequently, cluster analyses will give a more precise idea about the associations between different linguistic and extra-linguistic factors in the usage of HN. For example, based on our research experience, we can imagine the results of a cluster analysis of HN in 13th century chronicles with respect to following factors: social status of the referent, grammatical number, character importance. The cluster analysis would allow to distinguish the clusters per lexeme (Figure 7): 1st cluster – higher nobility titles *duc*, *prince*, *conte* referring to important characters with high level of agency in narration, 2nd cluster – *sergent*, *homme*, *gens* that are most commonly referred to collectively as a part of an army, 3rd cluster – *baron* and *chevalier* referring to characters of medium importance, both individually and collectively.

Figure 7

Depending on the results, the occurrences could be further clustered and/or annotated with additional variables.

Once the exploring of data completed, we will synthesize the results in order to establish multiple classifications combining several parameters, while representing the frequency of different subgroups. For example, a classification combining social group and gender parameters for 12th chronicles could produce following results (see table below).

Social	Nobility		Clergy		Bourgeois		Peasant	
	male	female	male	female	male	female	male	female
N of occurrences	8500 (85%)	100 (1%)	700 (7%)	100 (1%)	50 (0,5%)	25 (0,25%)	525 (5,25%)	0
N of types	60 (60%)	8 (8%)	10 (10%)	3 (3%)	9 (9%)	3 (3%)	4 (4%)	3 (3%)
Total occurrences	10000							
Total types	100							

Had those results been real, they would suggest that the dominant social group – noble males – are the best represented both numerically (number of occurrences) and lexically (number of types, i.e. different lexemes used as HN). On the other hand, male peasants – disposable military force in chronicles – would be well-enough represented numerically, but misrepresented lexically. Though those imaginary results are rather caricatural, they illustrate the type of outcomes we aim to obtain. Finally, the detected differences between subgroups will be tested for statistical significance through regression analysis.

I argue that no classification according to only one feature, or even pattern, can allow to grasp the complexity of the HN lexicon as a reflection and driver of social organization. The usage core analysis will thus result in multiple classifications per century that will combine HN in different subgroups depending on the classifying feature or pattern. Those classifications will be the ‘big picture’ HumaNS-CHANGE aims for. **Stage B. Reviewing historical records:** the interpretation of the classifications from Stage A in historical science perspective.

The patterns resulting from the stage A. analyses will have to be confronted to what is established by historians about social organization and its evolution based on Medieval Latin texts of which we have many more extant witnesses. Indeed, Medieval French law texts that have so far been largely overlooked by historical science; therefore, a special attention will be paid to the comparison between HN lexicon in Medieval French and Medieval Latin in documentary genre. On a more general level, the aim of stage B will be to assess the adequacy of the patterns resulting from stage A by answering questions of the following type:

- How do these patterns relate to historical analyses results?
- Do they add some yet overlooked elements?
- Do they reflect hierarchical and political differences between political systems covered by Medieval French (e.g. French Kingdom *vs* English kingdom in 13th century)?
- Is there a lag between social changes and their representation through language? If so, how is it dependent on the genre or historical period? *etc.*

Stage C. Synthesis: linguistics, pragmatics, history, anthropology: synthesis of the results as a way to understand interrelation between social organization and HN lexicon.

The objective of this last step will be to synthesize the found patterns, demonstrate their evolution overtime, as well as variation between genres, state their relation to historical realities and, by doing so, test the starting hypothesis by answering following questions:

- What is the performative impact of HN? Are they all performative in the same way?
- How does the HN lexicon reflect the agency of the referents?
- What factors are determinant in the choice of the precise HN by the speaker when any human being can receive multiple labels?
- How sensitive is the HN lexicon to major social changes?
- On a more general level, what does it teach us about the practices of labelling human beings in the society?

The synthesis will result in HumaNS-CHANGE's claim about the way **language reflects and shapes social organization** and changes within, which will be summarized in a programmatic volume. Ultimately, this stage is meant as a contribution to the understanding of the practices of labelling humans in a changing society.

a.4 Expected impact. HumaNS-CHANGE will have a multi-layered impact, every new stage adding a higher level of generalization.

1. Historical linguistics of Medieval French.

The results will enrich our knowledge about different linguistic aspects related to HN in Medieval French by

- providing semantic classifications
 - pointing out syntactic and morphological patterns
- and their evolution throughout the Medieval period.

Possibly, new linguistic items will be detected and described, which will allow to enrich lexicographical data. Moreover, HumaNS-CHANGE will represent an example of using multiple existing digital resources of Medieval French to constitute a representative project-driven corpus and provide open-access reusable annotated datasets. Finally, it will propose **new methods for semantic and lexical studies of MF** that have been in decline since 1980s due to a disenchantment in structuralist methodology.

2. Historical studies of Medieval French geographical zone

HumaNS-CHANGE will provide new evidence for historical studies of Medieval French. For instance, even though law texts start to be occasionally written in French from 13th century, until 16th century at least, Latin remains the main language of law in the geographical zone we are interested in; therefore, historical sciences working on documentary material (what can be summarized as 'law texts') tend to privilege Medieval Latin texts over French ones. The project will complete the results of historical analyses by extensive data from French texts of different genres. More generally, HumaNS-CHANGE will offer a **framework for historical studies based on Medieval French linguistic evidence**, as so far it has been done systematically only for Medieval Latin, (e.g. Perreaux 2016).

3. Pragmatics, linguistic anthropology and other social sciences

HumaNS-CHANGE will complete kinship and personal name research traditions by proposing a methodology for using the linguistic description of HN lexica as a tool for the study of social relations, structures of power and their evolution overtime. Ultimately, HumaNS-CHANGE will contribute to a better understanding of the **interrelation between language change and society evolution**.

At the same time, HumaNS-CHANGE will have a considerable impact on my research career. Since the beginning of my research journey, working on small-scale studies in semantics and pragmatics of Medieval French, I have consistently completed my linguistics background by findings in other social and human sciences. Presently, I understand that in order to take the next step and rise at a higher level of generalization in HN studies, I need to rely on a cross-disciplinary team that will join efforts in describing and synthesizing the role of HN lexicon in social change. Finally, grasping the big picture on a material I have expertise in – Medieval French – will represent an important step towards my long-term research goal: exploring the interrelation between HN and social organization universally.

Section b. Methodology

b.1. Team. My research background puts me in a privileged position for the role of Principal Investigator (PI) of HumaNS-CHANGE, as I have expertise or relevant knowledge in all the fields it will address.

1. Historical linguistics of Medieval French: expertise. As the core of the project is the study of the usage of HN, it is essential that the PI has a thorough expertise in historical linguistics of Medieval French. I have

worked on several lexical items studying closely their linguistic behavior. The semasiological perspective of my research along with my teaching experience (see B1 section b. CV and Track Record) allowed me to acquire expertise in linguistic analysis in different subfields of historical linguistics of Medieval French: semantics and pragmatics in the first place, but also syntax and morphology, as well as graphic system change. Furthermore, as I have benefited from a complete research freedom from my Master's studies, I had the occasion to test different semantic theories for the description of the same object.

2. Medieval French texts, their classification, production mode and accessibility: expertise. In order to palliate the impossibility of accessing the “real” linguistic competence of the medieval speakers, a solid knowledge of Medieval French texts and their specificity is required. My research allowed me to work on different medieval genres (epic texts, romance, chronicles, religious texts, law texts, fabliaux) and to acquire sufficient understanding of their main features, evolution and modes of production. Moreover, my background allows me to navigate effectively through numerous online resources that are essential in Medieval French studies (dictionaries, corpora, databases). All in all, it enables me to constitute effectively a corpus that is large enough, usable for extracting considerable amount of data and as representative of the written standard evolution as possible.

3. History of Medieval French-speaking geographical zone from 9th to 15th century: solid knowledge Since my PhD research, I have consistently linked the semantic evolution of studied HN to major changes in feudal society. In particular, my research on the feudal HN provided me with a solid knowledge of the bibliography in historical medieval studies and the overall evolution of Medieval society.

4. Historical pragmatics, linguistic anthropology and other social sciences: expertise/relevant knowledge. My research has equipped me with expertise in historical pragmatics of Medieval French. The semasiological nature of my research resulted in my early interest in HN used as terms of address (Geylikman 2017b). After the thesis I have contributed to the creation of the CDF corpus (*Corpus de dialogues en français*, see B1 section b. CV and Track record) designed for historical pragmatics studies and have myself performed excellent research disseminated through talks and articles on terms of address in Medieval French (recent talk in Diachro XI, May 2024; Geylikman 2022a, in preparation). The pragmatic and sociolinguistic perspectives allowed me to grasp the importance of considering relations between speakers, as well as their characteristics (gender, social group) in linguistic analysis. Moreover, working on *personne*, I got acquainted with key concepts for social and human sciences such as social actor or identity (Geylikman 2024). Finally, during the current ANR fellowship I acquired relevant knowledge of works in linguistic anthropology.

5. Statistical analysis for SHS: relevant knowledge. Thanks to the CoMil Summer School (June 2024, Université Paris 8), I have a relevant understanding of the opportunities the statistical analysis offers for exploring and analyzing categorical data in social and human sciences, as well as the way the data should be processed in order to allow further analysis. Since June 2024, I have already implemented elements of statistical analysis in my research and contributions (Geylikman submitted, in preparation; talk in LLcD conference in September 2024, Sorbonne Université).

Furthermore, I have proven my **leadership qualities** through cross-disciplinary workshop organizing, editing proceedings, and coordinating a project in its crucial stage (see B1 section b. CV and Track record). Finally, I have consistently demonstrated **scientific independence**: while receiving excellent guidance from my mentors, since I started research during my Master's degree, I have always chosen the object, goals and methods myself. As a result, most of my publications and talks draw on individual research.

HumaNS-CHANGE is a natural continuation of my research path, but in order to take the next step, I need to bring together a cross-disciplinary team. The team will thus include three Postdoctoral Researchers – an expert in Historical Linguistics of Medieval French (PDLing), an expert in the political history of Medieval French-speaking zone (PDHist), an expert in linguistic anthropology (PDAnt) – and a data scientist (DS) specialized in statistical analysis for SHS. As the project is meant to be a fruit of methodological collaboration across disciplines, it is essential for the team to be fully committed to the project. Therefore, HumaNS-CHANGE will rely on a team of early-career researchers, leaving senior expertise to the external advisory board (see b.3 Risk management and feasibility). As PI's role will be held through Postdoctoral Researcher position, all the team will dedicate 100% of their working time to HumaNS-CHANGE.

b.2. Work plan. HumaNS-CHANGE will be carried out in 60 months in three stages, each one containing at least one Workpackage (WP):

	duration	timeline	team	events	publications	resources
Stage A: WP1-3	60 months (m.)	m. 1-42	PI, PDLing, DS	5 talks kick-off	4 articles	open-access annotated data and plots; website dedicated to the project
Stage B: WP4-6		m. 25-48	PI, PDHist, DS	5 talks 1 workshop	5 articles 1 special issue	
Stage C: WP7-9		m. 42-60	all team	3 talks 1 conference	6 articles 1 volume	

Stage A. WP1, months 0-6: Data collection. 0-6 months. WP1 will contain three tasks – corpus selection, lexeme selection and data extraction – and will be executed by PI and PDLing.

Task 1. Corpus selection. While designing HumaNS-CHANGE project, I had several options when it comes to the corpus: (a) either creating a new corpus with a project-driven annotation, or (b) using one existing corpus with an already homogenous annotation. The option (a) has been excluded from the beginning of the project design: my experience of collaboration in Digital Humanities suggests that the creation of a relevant user-friendly and sustainable online resource should be a project in itself and often has to be done to the detriment of the research constituent. As for option (b), there is no Medieval French corpus that would represent all genres in a satisfying manner; combining different corpora appears essential for maximizing representativity. Therefore, I have opted for (c): select the most relevant texts we from the existing corpora of Medieval French that can be used advantageously for the purpose: BFM22, FABLIAUX-V0, ConDÉ, MICLE, CHRONIQUES, DocLing, AND corpus, Frantext, ALMA (see Resources for references).

Current estimation: 150 texts of a total of 3,5 000 000 tokens; genres *fiction* (epic texts, romance, lyric poetry), *chronicles*, *religious texts* (sermons, Bible translations, hagiographies, theatre), *didactical texts*, *scientific texts*, *law texts* (charters, *coutumes*, trial proceedings).

Task 2. Lexeme selection. By focusing on the HN lexicon, our project will avoid both the vagueness of the “semantic field” studies and the randomness of lexical case studies, being driven in item selection by only two criteria: the item has to be a common noun and to denote the human being in any type of context. Speaking of grammatical category, nominalized adjectives could be included in the list (ex. *belle* eng. *fem.* “beauty, beautiful”); but they will only be collected and annotated once the team is sure to be able to process of the data with “proper” nouns.

As there is no conventional list of HN in Medieval French, in order to detect the lexemes, we will proceed in two steps: (1) extraction of HN from the common nouns index query in BFM22 – the closest to the representativity of written genres evolution corpus of Medieval French; (2) manual detection of lexical items that would have been overlooked on step (2) through reading of one text per genre and per half-century (when applicable). The latter step will allow to detect nouns and adjectives that are used as *ad hoc* nominalizations (e.g. *casseroles*, eng. ‘pot’ meaning ‘stupid woman’). Once the selection completed, we will synthesize the information on every item from the entries of the following Medieval French dictionaries – FEW, DEAF, TL, GdF, DMF – following the framework of Robert Martin’s articles in DMF.

Current estimation: approx. 400 lexical items.

Task 3: Extraction of data. Once the selection completed, we will extract the total number of every item occurrences from all the corpora with 30 words before, 30 words after the pivot. For lemmatized corpora, the search will be performed by lemma, in other cases – by graphic forms through Regular Expression formula. Current estimation: 50000-80000 overall occurrences to process.

WP2, months 3-33: Annotation. This stage will represent the core of the project and is meant to be the most time-consuming; it will be executed by PI and PDLing.

Over past decades, NLP tools have proven their relevance for studies in different fields of linguistics. Thus, papers in historical computational semantics appear regularly in the *Journal of Historical Linguistics* over last years (e.g. Georgakopoulos & Polis 2021; Amaral *et al.* 2023; Law 2023). Indeed, distributional semantic studies show outstanding results, allowing to detect meaning variation per genre (Perrone *et al.*), or concept evolution from the point of view of historical science (e.g. Perreaux 2011, 2016), visualize synonymy (e.g. DES: Dictionnaire Électronique des Synonymes¹¹), polysemy and even semantic change (for an overview, see Boleda 2020). It is also extensively used for discourse analysis (see DYLEN resource¹², Truan 2021), and is more and more implemented in anthropology and culture studies (Berger & Packard 2022). Nevertheless, medieval corpora appear too small for smooth machine learning; and most importantly, HumaNS-CHANGE’s goal is not properly semantic and requires annotation of extra-linguistic features that are not deductible from strictly linguistic context. Therefore, staying open to potential modifications of the annotation strategy during the project, given the impressive rate of development of digital humanities and especially language processing by artificial intelligence, as of today a partly manual annotation appears the most appropriate for HumaNS-CHANGE needs. Finally, my research experience, as well as its anthropological aiming, suggests the importance of ‘listening’ to our subjects – i.e. knowing the texts and reading the occurrences we are studying.

While a number of variables will be annotated automatically (e.g. all the metadata on the text, or else grammatical gender) a part of factors will have to undergo semi-manual annotation (through Regex formula combined with a manual analysis of ambiguous examples (e.g. indirect speech), or else manual annotation (e.g. the relation of the speaker to the addressee for TA). As the frequency of different HN will be unequal –

¹¹ <https://crisco4.unicaen.fr/des/synonymes/tronc>

¹² <https://dysten.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/>

for example, in BFM22 (9th-15th century 7328715 tokens) we find 23496 occurrences of the lemma *roi* (eng. “king”) against 12 occurrences of the lemma *musicien* (eng. “musician”), for the items that will count more than 1000 occurrences per genre and per century, we will annotate the automatic part fully, then select random samples for manual annotation.

We will start by annotating small random samples in order to assess annotation pace and, if necessary, adapt the corpus accordingly (task 1). Then the corpus will be annotated per chronological segments: 9th-12th century¹³ (task 2), 13th century (task 3), 14th century (task 4), 15th century (task 5). A re-evaluation of the annotation pace will occur at month 18. Once the annotation completed, we will synthesize the results numerically for every item per genre and per century (or half-century), which will allow to investigate both the variation between genres and the change in diachrony. For polysemic lexemes, variation per meaning will also be synthesized.

WP2: Tasks and milestones	Deadline (months)
Task 1: samples	m. 6
Task 2: 9 th -12 th	m. 15
Milestone: re-evaluating annotation pace	m. 18
Task 3: 13 th	m. 21
Task 4: 14 th	m. 25
Task 5: 15 th	m. 30

WP3, months 24-42: Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis will be held by DS. To date, I assume that the most relevant will be to explore data through Multiple Correspondence analysis, then cluster analyses and further determine assess what detected differences are statistically significant through regression analysis. Nevertheless, I will stay open to suggestions by DS who may choose other types of statistical analyses depending on the observations and assumptions made by PI and PDLing during annotation. Statistical analysis will follow the chronological order of the segments equivalent to WP2.

Although I intend to allow consultation and visualization of the results of data processing through the website of the project, I do not aim for a dynamic explorable online resource. Indeed, my experience of collaboration for Digital Humanities projects suggests that the creation of a relevant user-friendly and sustainable online resource (e.g. database, corpus) should be a project in itself and often has to be done to the detriment of the research constituent. Instead, I intend to focus on getting impactful scientific results and promoting them through scientific publications and international events.

WP3: Tasks	Deadline (months)
Task 1: 9 th -13 th	m. 33
Task 2: 14 th -15 th	m. 39
Task 3: synthesis on evolution	m. 42

Stage B. WP 4, months 24-33: bibliography overview and framework, PDHist will be in charge of synthesizing works in history and historical anthropology of Medieval French-speaking Europe in respect to the evolution of structures of power, as well as cultural representations on various social groups. This WP is meant as a preparation for WP6; it will result in a framework of chronological and conceptual milestones that will enable further comparison of HN usage with historical realities. **WP5, months 28-38: MF vs Medieval Latin law texts**, PDHist: The goal of this WP will be to produce a comprehensive comparative analysis of HN lexicon usage in Medieval French and Medieval Latin on documentary texts material. **WP6, months 32-48: Reviewing historical records**: WP6 will be essentially analytical, driven by PDHist’s expertise. The goal will be to confront the patterns resulting from Stage A to the framework of social change prepared in WP4. Potentially, it will require **WP6a** – further annotation of certain samples and additional statistical analysis performed by DS and coordinated this time by PDHist.

Stage C. WP7, months 30-36: bibliography overview and framework. Similarly to WP4, during **WP7**, PDAnt proceed to an overview of bibliography in order to prepare a methodological framework for further analyses of the results from stages A-B in anthropological perspective. In **WP8, months 36-48: HN in anthropological perspective**, PDAnt will put those results in perspective of what is known on agency of

¹³ The number and dimensions of the Early French texts from 9th to 11th are very modest.

power and cultural representations universally; it can require further statistical analysis (**WP8a**). Finally, **WP9, months 42-60: *Vademecum* for HN studies by SHS** will require knowledge and skills of the whole team who will collaborate on a statement on the way HN evolution sheds light on social change. This final statement will take the form of a joint open-access publication that will propose a methodological framework for cross-disciplinary studies of HN in diachrony and illustrate it by the results obtained by HumaNS-CHANGE on Medieval French material. De Gruyter publishing house has already expressed their interest for the future publication of the volume (Letter of intent containing estimated costs provided by De Gruyter).

Management and dissemination:

WP10, months 0-60. *Management*. Throughout the project, PI will be in charge of scientific coordination both for the project and its outcomes. Thus, drawing on my experience in project coordination (ConDÉ project, see B1 section b CV and Track Record), I will organize monthly interviews with every team member in order to assess task's progress in respect to the project's calendar; moreover, a shared tasks table will be uploaded to the Host Institution cloud service enabling a regular follow up by all the members of the project, as well as the advisory board.

PDLing will divide his/her time between research and project managing, being in charge of more technical tasks: purchasing equipment, event and travel organizing. Finally, PI and DS will be in charge of sustainability of the project by regularly uploads of data to the GitHub of the project and monthly backups on a dedicated hard drive.

WP11, months 0-60. *Dissemination*. In order to advertise HumaNS-CHANGE methodology and results and obtain relevant feedback from the scientific community, the team will invest considerable time and effort in project's dissemination. Thus, the aim will be to publish approx. **15 articles** (at least 8 in Open-Access). Targeted journals: *Journal of French Language studies*, *Journal of Historical Linguistics*, *Journal of Historical Pragmatics*, *Journal of Pragmatics*, *Language*, *Journal of Medieval History*, *The Historical Journal*, *Journal of Social History*. Furthermore, the goal is to present at least **13 talks/posters** in international conferences. Finally, HumaNS-CHANGE team will organize several events: a **workshop** on combining the existing corpora for representativity in a major historical linguistics conference (e.g. International Conference for Historical Linguistics) at Stage A; a **workshop** on studying lexica from historical perspective in a major Medieval studies conference (e.g. International Medieval Congress) at Stage B resulting in a special issue editing; a **conference** on HN in diachrony including a workshop summarizing the final programmatic volume at Stage C to be hosted by Host Institution. Furthermore, PDLing will be in charge of creating and maintaining the project's website on an open-access platform offering ready-to-use templates, where team members will post quarterly blogs on work progress and announcements of related events (e.g. <https://fr.hypotheses.org/>). PI and DS will ensure the replicability of the research by providing **open-access annotated reusable data** through the GitHub of the project.

Figure 5

b.3. Risk management and feasibility. As every large-scale project, HumaNS-CHANGE will raise several issues that our methodology and coordination skills will have to counterbalance.

Thus, the two major advantages of HumaNS-CHANGE – (1) **large amount of data to process** through partly manual annotation and (2) **cross-disciplinary nature** of the project – are at the same time the two factors that can put project's feasibility at risk.

We will address risk (1) by making small sample tests for assessing annotation rate and adapting the corpus if necessary, preserving the balance between representativity and feasibility. Moreover, for items of more than 1000 occurrences per genre + century, we will annotate the automatic and semi-automatic part fully, then *max.* 200 randomized occurrences manually. Finally, we will segment the corpus per century and proceed to annotation accordingly. It appears more beneficiary than to segment it by genre, as it will allow to get first results on genre variation and on diachronic change, as 100 years can still offer evidence of both linguistic and social evolution. Hence, once the data is annotated for the 12th century texts, it will be possible to attack statistical analysis, while continuing the annotation of the rest of the corpus. This approach will ensure we will answer the research questions for at least a part of the studied period.

Although cross-disciplinary nature is essential when answering big questions in social and human sciences, it represents an important challenge, especially when it comes to adapting methodologies from different fields for the needs of the same project. In order to address risk (2), throughout the project, PI and other team members will have to remain open-minded as to the extent of the necessary adaptations.

Moreover, an advisory board will be formed including senior researchers from all the fields related to the project. The project will start by an offline kick-off meeting with the board in order to sharpen the methodology of Stage A. Subsequently, hybrid yearly meetings with the board will be scheduled with, in addition, individual consultations with board members that will occur *ad hoc*. Members of the advisory board: Dr. Wiltrud Mihatsch, Universität Tübingen (linguistics of HN); Dr. Sabine Tittel, Universität Heidelberg (Medieval French lexicology and lexicography); Dr. Martin Aurell, Université de Poitiers (medieval history); Dr. Didier Lett, Université Paris Cité (medieval anthropology); Dr. Cécile Leguy, LACITO, Université Sorbonne Nouvelle (linguistic anthropology).

Moreover, organizing project-related workshops and sharing results in various international conferences in linguistics, history and linguistic anthropology will allow to receive extensive feedback on the project methodology and findings from the social and human science community.

Finally, being aware of competition from industry for highly skilled profiles in statistical analysis, as well as the fact that Junior Researchers prioritize permanent positions over limited research contracts, we will anticipate potential contract disruptions by a thorough technical and methodological documentation of all the tasks, as well as reports from monthly monitoring of the project's progress.

b.4 Perspectives for further research

As we have stated several times earlier, human nouns appear as a key research object for social and human sciences. Therefore, a 5-years project will not be able to explore all possibilities that a thorough linguistic description of a HN lexicon in diachrony will offer. For HumaNS-CHANGE, I choose to focus on its impact on and interrelation with social organization, by treating questions of performativity, agency and cultural representations. But even from my current perspective I can see at least three big directions to be taken afterwards: HN as part of human reference (personal names, pronouns and HN as a system), identity studies (expressing and shaping human identities), categorization studies (humans categorizing other humans and themselves through language, naming strategies). I am confident that, if funded, HumaNs-CHANGE will give a start to a long line of works in social and human sciences that will bring us closer to understanding ourselves.

RESOURCES

Dictionaries

ALMA = ALMA – Modeling of Knowledge Networks in Medieval Romance Speaking Europe Based on Linguistic Data, Heidelberg Akademie der Wissenschaften

AND corpus = textbase search possible in Anglo-Norman Dictionary <https://anglo-norman.net/>

BFM22 = Base de Français Médiéval [En ligne]. Lyon: ENS de Lyon, Laboratoire IHRIM, 2022, <txm.bfm-corpus.org>.

ConDÉ = Larrivée, Pierre et Mathieu Goux (eds) (2021) corpus ConDÉ, version Bêta 1.0, Caen, CRISCO (EA 4255) et PDN (MRSH) de l'Université de Caen. URL: <https://txm-crisco.huma-num.fr/txm/>

CRONIQUE = Larrivée, Pierre (Ed), 2023, corpus HIGH-TECH, v. 1.5, Caen (France), CRISCO (EA 4255).

DocLing = Les plus anciens documents linguistiques galloromans, Édition électronique dirigée par Martin Glessgen en partenariat avec Hélène Carles, Frédéric Duval et Paul Videsott, Troisième édition (2016) <http://www.rose.uzh.ch/docling/>

FABLIAUX-V0-1 = Corpus FABLIAUX-V0-1, (2023), C. Pierreville (éd.). Publié en ligne par l'ENS de Lyon dans la Base de français médiéval.

Frantext = ATILF. Base textuelle Frantext (En ligne). ATILF-CNRS & Université de Lorraine. 1998-2024. <https://www.frantext.fr/>

MICLE-PREVIEW = Larrivée, Pierre et Poletto, Cecilia (eds) (2023) corpus MICLE-PREVIEW, v. 0.9, Caen (France) / Francfort (Allemagne), CRISCO (EA 4255) / Institut für Romanische Sprachen und Literaturen.

On-line corpora and databases:

AND = Anglo-Norman Dictionary, <https://anglo-norman.net/>

FEW = Wartburg, W., et al., (1922-2002), Französisches Etymologisches Wörterbuch. Eine darstellung des galloromanischen sprachschatzes, 25 vol., Bonn/Heidelberg/Leipzig-Berlin/Basel, Klopp/Winter/Teubner/Zbinden.

DMF = Dictionnaire du Moyen Français, version 2023 (DMF 2023). ATILF - CNRS & Université de Lorraine. URL: <http://www.atilf.fr/dmf>

DEAF = Dictionnaire étymologique de l'ancien français (DEAF). K. Baldinger/S. Dörr/F. Möhren/T. Städtler/S. Tittel/ Niemeyer, Tübingen/Presses universitaires de Québec, 1974-2019

GdF = Godefroy, Frédéric, Dictionnaire de l'ancienne langue française et de tous ses dialectes du XI^e au XV^e siècle, Paris, F. Viewig, 1881-1902

TL = Tobler, Adolf & Lommatzsch, Erhard, Altfranzösisches Wortebuch, [1928, 1930], Stuttgart-Wiesbaden, Franz Steiner Verlag, 2002.

Manuals and encyclopedias:

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**Appendix: All current grants and on-going / submitted grant applications of the PI
(Funding ID)**

Mandatory information (does not count towards page limits)

Current research grants (Please indicate "No funding" when applicable):

<i>Project Title</i>	<i>Funding source</i>	<i>Amount (Euros)</i>	<i>Period</i>	<i>Role of the PI</i>	<i>Relation to current ERC proposal¹⁴</i>
HumaNs-MF Call ANR Access ERC Starting Grant 2023	Agence Nationale de Recherche (ANR), France	185 586,12	01/10/2023- 30/05/2025	PI; Position: Postdoctoral researcher; Tasks: publication of previous unfunded research results; preparation of the ERC Starting Grant 2025 application	The ANR Access ERC Starting funding is a competitive Post Doc fellowship that enables promising junior researchers to prepare a competitive ERC Starting Grant application. Since the beginning of the fellowship, I have worked on improving my track record through publications and international conference attending, as well as designing the HumaNS- CHANGE project for the ERC Starting Grant application. No task planned for HumaNS-CHANGE has been undertaken during current fellowship.

On-going / submitted grant applications (Please indicate "None" when applicable):

<i>Project Title</i>	<i>Funding source</i>	<i>Amount (Euros)</i>	<i>Period</i>	<i>Role of the PI</i>	<i>Relation to current ERC proposal²</i>
None					

¹⁴ Describe clearly any scientific overlap between your ERC application and the current research grant or on-going grant application.